

PREPARATION OF A MIXED COORDINATION COMPOUND COBALT-II NITRATE HEXAHYDRATE WITH QUINAZOLINE-4-ONE AND 3-INDOLYLACETIC ACID ON “AMBER” PLANTS OF THE PHASEOLUS AUREUS VARIETY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7536612>

Abstract: *The biochemical effects of the coordination compound of cobalt-II nitrate quinazolin-4-one with 3-indolyl acetic acid in the “amber” plants grades Phaseolus aureus have been studied. Cobalt is an important trace element for plants and an important biogenic element in the soil, mainly in the form of the Co²⁺ cation, which participates in redox reactions in plant organisms for the implementation of various mineral and organic compounds. Cobalt compounds are mainly soluble in mineral acids, so we want to show that the coordination compound containing this trace element, formed by the nitrate salt with quinazolin-4-one, serves as a source of plant nutrition.*

Key words: *cobalt-II nitrate, quinazolin-4-one, 3-indolyl acetic acid, “amber” plants grades Phaseolus aureus, coordination compound, biochemical effect, trace element, mineral and organic compounds, redox reaction, biogenic element, source of nutrients.*

Heterocyclic compounds are widely distributed in nature (drugs, alkaloids, pigments, and the others are included in the sentence of heterocyclic compounds), the magnitude of their importance in biological processes, in the reception of dyes and medicines, as well as the availability of the possibility of obtaining them from the waste products of Agriculture, from coal tar, which is the basis of the development of the Currently, two-thirds of the research conducted by chemist scientists around the world is aimed at the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds and the study of their properties. These compounds are easily formed from open-chain compounds and, as a result of the rupture of the ring, they again turn into open-chain compounds.

Some of the heterocyclic compounds differ in their properties from other organic compounds, and in little or in many ways repeat the properties of aromatic compounds, which are difficult to combine reactions, such as aromatic compounds, while they are easy to exchange reactions.

As a result of the interaction of 2 π -bond and non-paired free electrons in the heteroatom in the ring, an electronic cloud of adhesion in the ring occurs, and the ring is located in one plane, but the stability of the sequence of π -electrons in the benzene ring and heterocycle will be different. In addition to the exchange and deposition reactions characteristic for aromatic hydrocarbons, the exchange of heteroatom in the ring for heterocyclic compounds is also characteristic of the outgoing reactions with the opening of the rings [1].

External indicators of cobalt deficiency in plants are similar to signs of nitrogen deficiency. They are manifested by a slowing of plant growth, yellowing and chlorosis of the leaves, a decrease in the period of development of the crop. The most noticeable drawback of this microelement is in the pulses. In this case, the activity of the nodes is low, as well as the intensity of the formation of bactericidal tissue and the mobility of the bactericides decreases.

Lack of cobalt in the composition of plants leads to a lack of this element in the nutrition of animals, which leads to the development of avitaminosis in them, slowing the formation of hemoglobin, proteins, nucleic acids and the appearance of endemic goiter. Lack of cobalt in the grass occurs when the amount of cobalt in the soil is less than 5 mg/kg. A critical level of this microelement in the dry mass of plant food, which determines the successful development of animals, is 0,08-0,10 mg / kg.

The excess of cobalt causes saturation of the edges and ends of the leaves of the plant with this element, which manifests itself in the whiteness and death of these places [2].

In our earlier work, we have organized alkylation reactions of quinazolin-4-on, and - tions and its gamologists, as well as their effect on the body of plants and animals.

We took aim at obtaining stabilizers that are today's is the main function and examining the impact of their oscillations on growth and development.

The experimental part

1. Synthesis of quinazolin-4-one.

0,2 moles of o-aminobenzoic acid and 0,2 moles of formamide are put in a chemical round retort. The reaction mixture was heated in an alloy of Vudd in a reverse refrigerator for one hours at 150°C, then cooled to room temperature.

When put in cold water, white crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

The chemical reaction of the process is carried out as follows.

2. Effect of quinazolin-4-one with 3-indolyl fatty acid.

0,2 mol of quinazolin-4-one and 0,2 mol of 3-indolyl fatty acid are poured into a round retort. The reaction mixture was heated in a water bath in an inverted refrigerator for 3 hours at a temperature of 80-90°C, then the resulting combination is cooled to room temperature. When the formed crystals were soaked in water, yellowish crystals were formed, filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

Cobaltate (II)-nitrate and quinazolin-4-one a coordinate combination of with 3-indole fatty acid.

Effect product 0,2 mol quinazolin-4-one with 3-indolyl fatty acid 0,1 mol cobalt (II)-nitrate porcelain is mixed mechanically for 3 hours with a mixer in a mortar. Every 10-15 minutes porcelain mixed is cleaned by scraping around the air and the mixer. The formula of the combination can be expressed as follows.

In the study of the processes of biochemical action of cobalate (II)-nitrate and quinazolin-4-one on the “amber” variety of the *Phaseolus aureus* plant of the coordination compound formed by 3-indole fatty acid, we carried out the following processes.

Exactly why was the same variety selected? The main reason for this is that the plant of the *Phaseolus aureus* plant “amber” is a plant belonging to the angular space, in the root of which the root vegetable bacteria live together and have the property of absorbing molecular nitrogen in the air. We planted the molecular nitrogen contained in the atmospheric air through the roots of the plant to be absorbed in the soil as well as the microelement of Co^{2+} in the formation of vegetable bacteria is of great importance, and based on this combination, we obtained an authorized certificate.

It also has a heterocyclic compound pyrimidine ring, which is part of the II compound we synthesized. It determines direct vital processes, such as plant, animal and human organisms (Deoxyribonucleic acid, ribonucleic acid).

Our expected results in the experiment are a technique from the following stages.

1. The result of the experiment was the preparation of 2,5% and 5% li solutions of the II product in distilled water.
2. Seeds of 20 pieces are soaked for 5 hours and 10 hours in a 2,5% solution.
3. Seeds of 20 pieces are ived for 5 hours and 10 hours in a 5% solution.

The effect of the resulting substance II on the germination of seeds.

Seeds were placed in a thermostat at an equal distance in 4 petri dishes and 1 petri dish in 20 pieces, total in 5 petri dish. Temperature 27°C , humidity level 40%. For 5 hours, the ripening processes were observed in 2,5% solution compared to the ripening processes in 10% solution, for 5 hours, the ripening processes were observed in 5% solution compared to 10 hours in 10% solution. The speed of growth of the roots was carried out in this way.

We believe that if the seeds are planted in a 2.5% solution to the hanging wire of the root for 5 hours, then it is desirable to count.

In place of the conclusion, we must say that this complex organic compound plays an important role in the processes of hemopoiesis. Cobalt in plants is a microelement necessary for the assimilation of molecular nitrogen, promotes the formation of nodular bacteria in the root system of leguminous crops. Cobalt accumulates in the wood of the plant, accelerating its growth.

participates in the exchange of oxen, that is, it is an important nutrient of plant growth processes (including helps to stretch the cell membranes).

This metal is involved in the cellular reproduction of leaves (an increase in the thickness and volume of the mesophylline, the size and number of cells in the parenchyma of the columnar and Nebula leaf). In addition, Cobalt increases the overall water content of plants and thereby increases the drought resistance of crops.

Through the concentration of chloroplasts and pigments in the leaves, it was found that the effect of cobalt on the formation and functioning of photosynthesis of plants is of great importance.

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